

STATISTICAL RESEARCH OF THE INCREASE OF POPULATION EMPLOYMENT

Surkhandarya region

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Abstract: In this article, the employment of the population in our country is deeply analyzed, the practical importance and theoretical foundations of ensuring the employment of the population are considered. It was also discussed how urgent it is to ensure employment of the population in the current period and the reforms being carried out in this regard in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: *labor market, analysis, global pandemic, forecast, population, employment, unemployment, guaranteed income, educational services, population employment, action strategy.*

AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISHNING STATISTIK TADQIQOTI

Surxondaryo viloyati

Statistika boshqarmasi

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada yurtimizda aholi bandligi chuqur tahlil qilingan bo`lib, aholi bandligini ta`minlashning amaliy ahamiyati va nazariy asoslari ko`rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, hozirgi davrda aholi bandligini ta`minlash naqadar dolzarb ekanligi va O`zbekiston Respublikasida shu borada olib borilayotgan islohatlar haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: *mehnat bozori, tahlil, global pandimiya, prognoz, aholi,*

bandlik, ishsizlik, kafolatli daromad, ta'lim xizmatlari, aholi bandligi, harakatlar strategiyasi.

СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЗАНЯТОСТИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ

Сурхандарьинская область
Сурхандарьинская область
Статистическое управление
Алимов Усман Иброхимович

Аннотация: В данной статье глубоко анализируется занятость населения в нашей стране, рассматривается практическое значение и теоретические основы обеспечения занятости населения. Также было обсуждено актуальность обеспечения занятости населения в текущий период и проводимые в связи с этим реформы в Республике Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: рынок труда, анализ, глобальная пандемия, прогноз, население, занятость, безработица, гарантированный доход, образовательные услуги, занятость населения, стратегия действий.

In front of most countries of the world, strengthening the social protection of the population and reducing poverty remains one of the main tasks. In particular, during the global pandymia period, this showed its obvious proof. The threatening situation, as it is now, will lead to the derailment of the economy of many countries and a decrease in the standard of living of the population, as well as an increase in the problem of unemployment. Of course, in such a situation, it will be more up to the state to ensure the employment of the population and improve their living conditions. This requires the implementation of drastic measures in this direction at the level of Public Policy. Therefore, increasing the employment of

the population is now defined as a priority of the country's policy, and the provision of the population with new jobs and a guaranteed source of income, qualified medical and educational services, decent living conditions is one of the main goals. In particular, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on employment of the population” of 2020 was adopted, which serves as the basis for the creation of a new stage in the regulation of relations in the field of employment of the population[1].

Employment is an important factor in increasing the standard of living of the population. As the president of our Republic noted: “...the effect of the economic reforms and social changes we carry out is primarily measured by the extent to which it affects the material condition and well-being of the population, the increase in its level and quality of Life” [2]. These changes were initially manifested through Labor Relations, creating the need for the formation and development of the labor market. The development of this market activity is important in solving the problems of employment of the population. In this regard, the law “on employment of the population” and the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan are an important legal basis in the process of forming the labor market in our country.

In addition, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-60 of January 28, 2022 adopted the “new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2022-2026” [3]. In this strategy, the activities of the Institute of assistant mayor of the district (city) were determined by the new system on issues of employment and poverty reduction. It was also given the task of developing a draft of the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which provides for measures to place returning citizens from abroad at-Address work, retrain them through vocational training and attract them to entrepreneurial activities within the framework of the” state program for the organization of new jobs and promotion of population employment ” until March 2022. This represents the relevance of this research topic. In 2017-2021, in the strategy of action on the five priority

areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tasks of ensuring the employment and earning of the population through innovative development of the economy of our country, consistent continuation of active investment policy, creation of new modern enterprises, comprehensive support of entrepreneurship are established. In the address of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Supreme Assembly on January 24, 2020, it was noted: “we should apply new jobs to entrepreneurs in every possible way, to raise them on our shoulders, if they are honest.”

In the conditions of modernization of the economy, ensuring employment of the population is one of the important issues. Because, the presence of the problem of unemployment is an integral feature of the market economy. Therefore, by increasing the employment of the population, the expansion of the country's production and the development of activities related to the further improvement of the living standards of the population are counted from the current tasks of today. The above-mentioned regulatory documents form an important basis for ensuring their employment in improving the well-being of the population. After all, despite the Guarantee established by the laws and codes cited, in 2021, “while there is a need to employ more than 1 million 441 people a year in our country, last year the Employment Assistance Centers employed only 393 thousand people, or 27.3 percent. The main reason for this is due to outdated forms and methods in business activities and formality in solving employment problems” [4]. This cited situation determines the relevance of the chosen topic, ensuring the proportionality and infrastructure development of the labor market in our country, paying special attention to the issue of reducing the level of unemployment.

In the conditions of macroeconomic stabilization of the current economy, it is important to ensure employment of the population, solve employment within the framework of the system of market relations, that is, to form in practice real supply and demand for labor, new mechanisms for the regulation of employment

and the effective distribution of Labor, to create conditions under which Labor It also promotes the implementation of employment by the International Labor Organization under a labor program based on the principles of free, fair and safe. Employment as a socio-economic phenomenon can be defined as: employment is an activity in which citizens meet their own personal and social needs that do not contradict the legislation, bringing them wages or labor income.

It is advisable to create favorable conditions at the government level to create new jobs to increase the employment of the population and ensure its employment, ensure the proportionality and infrastructure development of the labor market, reduce the unemployment rate, fully implement the labor and entrepreneurial activity of the working population. The number of permanent residents of our country as of the beginning of 2022 is 35,271.3 thousand people. The population density was. km.ga the municipality has a population of 78.6 thousand people. Of this, the most densely populated areas are located in the city of Tashkent (1 sq. km.ga 6379.1 thousand people), Andijan (1 sq. km.ga 756.2 thousand people), Fergana (1 sq. km.ga 576.5 thousand people), Namangan (1 sq. km.ga 394.0 thousand people), Khorezm (1 sq. km.ga 317.9 thousand people), Samarkand (1 sq. km.ga 240.3 thousand people) and Syrdarya (1 sq. km.ga 205.5 thousand people) provinces. In 2021, the number of labor resources of the Republic is 19345.0 thousand people, which is 55.4% of the permanent population. The working population of the working age is 19258.1 thousand people, which is equal to 55.2% of the permanent population and 99.6% of labor resources. The number of workers under and over the working age is 86.9 thousand people, which is 0.2% of the permanent population and 0.4% of the labor resources[6].

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that the reforms carried out in our country are aimed at ensuring the employment of the population and improving their standard of living. However, it can also be seen that reforms in places are not being implemented effectively. For example, it is necessary to

introduce the practice of issuing micro loans to the unemployed, in particular through cash or plastic cards of credit funds of residents who are involved in livestock, rabbits, poultry and greenhouse activities[7]. Because the “provider” enterprises standing between the borrower and the bank are the main reason for the inefficiency of this practice. It is also necessary to strengthen the processes of employment of the unemployed population and increase wages.

Literature used:

1. Law No. 642 of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on employment of the population” of October 20, 2020. <https://lex.uz/docs/5055690>
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan together. (Speech at the joint session of the House of Commons on the occasion of the inauguration of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan), Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2016, pp. 15-16.
3. The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on employment of the population, Tashkent, East, 1998. B-32-33.
4. Shavkat Mirziyoyev: entrepreneurial subjects and new jobs will be the most basic criteria for assessing the activities of heads of Regions. <https://xs.uz>.
5. Radjabová G.U. Economic relations of employment in the Republic of Uzbekistan / / scientific electronic journal “Economics and innovative technologies”. № 6, November-December, 2018.
6. Alimov Usman Ibrahimovich " population employment in Uzbekistan: analysis and Forecast" 2022.
7. Yuldashev Zayir Toshkanovich. Methods of statistical analysis of population employment. 2022.